

FACTORS INFLUENCING GAMBLING BEHAVIOUR AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITIES IN RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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Keywords:

Gambling behavior, depression, peer pressure, income and residence.

Abstract: *The study investigated the factors influence of gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State. Using the description survey research design, the study was guided by 4 research questions and their corresponding null hypotheses. Sample of 300 students was drawn using the simple random sampling technique. For data collection five instruments were adapted for the study, the instruments are Income level (increase/decrease), Resident (rural/urban), Depression Scale (DS), Peer Pressure scale (PPS) and Gambling Behaviour scale (GBS). Reliability of the instrument using Cronbach Alpha yielded a coefficient of 0.76, 0.57, 0.72, 0.76, and 0.96 were obtained for the instruments are Income level, Resident, Depression, Peer Pressure and Gambling Behaviour. Simple regression and independent sample t-test were used to answer research questions and test the corresponding null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed that there is a significant relation between depression and gambling behaviour among undergraduate students, there is a significant relation between peer pressure and gambling behaviour among undergraduate students, there is a significant difference in the influence of income on gambling behaviour, and there is a significant difference in the influence of location on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State, it was recommended among others that gambling related issues should be legislated upon to curb the indiscriminate establishment of gambling centers' in the country, there should be a national committee that will be set up to streamline the frivolous and appealing*

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massive advertisement undertaking by gambling organization.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Gambling, wagering real money in order to win money is a social activity existing in almost all cultures and across development. A person is gambling whenever he or she takes the chance of losing money or belongings, and when winning or losing is decided mostly by chance. Gambling is a cultural, social and economic phenomenon that has pervaded most cultures in the world (Binde, 2005). For instance, with regard to its economic definition in Western societies, gambling is “wagering money or something of material value on an event with an uncertain outcome with the primary intent of winning additional money and/or material goods” (Dickerson and O’Connor, 2006).

In general, two of the most useful definitions of gambling are the following: first “using real money for a variety of types of activities, including: purchasing lottery tickets, betting on sports pools, playing cards, playing bingo, playing slot machines, betting on video games or video poker, and betting on other games of skill.” (Gupta and Derevensky, 1996); second “an activity that implies an element of risk, and that money, or something of sentimental or monetary value, could be won or lost by the participants.” (Ladouceur, Boudreault, Jacques, and Vitaro 1999).

The origins of gambling cannot be known for certain as it has been with mankind since pre historic times. Gambling and risk taking have been part of human culture since ancient times. Early accounts of gambling apparatus date back many centuries, with ivory dice recovered from Egyptian tombs made sometime before 1500 B.C. The Chinese, Japanese, Greeks and Romans were also known to practice games of skill and chance for amusement as early as 2300 B.C. (American Gaming Association, (AGA) 2003). Other findings indicate that the oldest back- gammon set to have ever been discovered is thought to be five thousand years old, was found in modern day Iran, and is older than the one found in ancient Mesopotamia, considered being the cradle of civilization (Sammut 2010). Gambling seems to be so important to mankind since it has been around longer than civilization itself and is present in every society, it is postulated that the origin of gambling might have come from the practice of divination that is the casting of sticks, stones and bones as a means of communication with the gods or spirits. Sammut (2010) explains that man’s nature to question his surroundings and to seek meaning in existence provided the basis for religion as well as science; and his fascination with the random can easily be seen to have given rise to the charm of gambling. Also it is indicated that Native Americans, believed gods determined their luck and chance and

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developed games and language related to gambling.

Tertiary students have been identified as an at risk group in relation to gambling. Many students have increased freedom at this age and are frequent internet users and fall into the age group (18-24 years) where problem gambling peaks (Gernstein et al 2010). Gambling is a type of conduct that has been distinguished to have genuine results on individuals' wellbeing, study habit, scholastic execution, and has been accounted for to be identified with some criminal related conduct (Oyebisi, Alao, and Popoola, 2012). Gambling has been commonly characterized as wagering or betting cash or something of significant worth on an occasion that has a questionable result with the likelihood of winning cash or materials (Korn and Shaffer, 1999). Betting customarily incorporates exercises, for example, betting at gambling clubs, on lotteries, creature hustling, card recreations, games, video lottery, and Internet card and gambling club diversions (Potenza, Fiellin, Heninger, Rounsaville and Mazure, 2002). A high rate of gambling has been found in various populaces crosswise over nations.

Individuals take part in a wide scope of betting practices, including playing the lottery, poker/cards for cash, club diversions (i.e., spaces/poker machines), horse dashing, wagering on games and web betting (McComb and Hanson, 2009).

A large Canadian prevalence survey of online gambling in Canada and various other countries, reported that student status and education level were significant predictors of online gambling (Wood and Williams, 2009), although prevalence studies of online gambling amongst students are limited. Another study that was done by Petry and Weinstock (2007), in an American university revealed that out of 1356 student participants, 23% reported ever gambling on the internet, 6.3% gambled online weekly and about a third of these online gamblers (who had ever gambled online) were classified as probable pathological gamblers. Studies have suggested that certain groups are more likely to be attracted to online gambling.

Gambling has been influenced by many factors, both psychologically and psychosocially. Some such factors include but not limited to depression, peer pressure, income level, place of residence etc.

According to Colman (2003) depression is a state of sadness, gloom, and pessimistic ideation, with loss of interest or pleasure in normally enjoyable activities, accompanied in severe cases by anorexia and consequent weight loss. Depression manifests as deep sorrow or grief, insomnia, loss of appetite, unpleasant mood, hopelessness, irritability, self-dislike, and suicidal tendencies. It has been observed that when gamblers loss bet, they show sign of depression and some have been reported to have committed suicide because of loss of bet.

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Gambling problems tend to co-occur with other mental disorders. Data from the population-based United States National Comorbidity Survey Replication (NCS-R) indicated that 96 % of respondents with lifetime pathological gambling also met diagnostic criteria for at least one other psychiatric disorder (Kessler, Hwang, LaBrie, Petukhova, Sampson, and Winters 2008). Major depression is one of the most common disorders that co-occur with problem gambling. The rate of comorbidity between lifetime pathological gambling and depression in the NCS-R was 39 % (Kessler et al. 2008). Data from another large population-based sample from the United States indicated a similar comorbidity rate between lifetime pathological gambling and major depression of 37 % (Petry, Stinson, and Grant, 2005). A recent meta-analysis reported an average prevalence rate of 23 % for comorbid major depression among problem and pathological gamblers from general population samples, combining current and lifetime estimates of the disorders (Lorains, Cowlshaw, and Thomas 2011).

There is some preliminary evidence that the presence of significant depressive symptoms may exacerbate the severity and worsen the prognosis of problem gambling. Thomsen, Callesen, Linnet, Kringelbach and Moller (2009) found that pathological gamblers with higher levels of depressive symptoms exhibited more severe gambling behavior compared to those low in depressive symptoms, in the form of increased urges to gamble and greater

duration of gambling during in-laboratory slot machine play. In a study of pathological gamblers who recently quit gambling, comorbid lifetime depression predicted a longer time to achieve stable abstinence from gambling (Hodgins, Peden, and Cassidy 2005) and negative affect was a commonly cited precipitant to relapse (Hodgins and el-Guebaly 2004). Thus, these studies suggest that depression may be associated with more severe gambling symptomatology among problem gamblers.

Peer pressure" can be described as the influence exerted by a peer group in encouraging a person to change his or her attitudes, values, or behaviours to conform to the group. According to Abdulbaqi, Tejideen, and Andajisegbede (2019) stated that there is significant relationship between peer influence and engagement in gambling. A person that is associated with friend that participates in gambling is also vulnerable to gambling related activities. This can be justified based on the fact that an individual who fails to conform to group norms may face social rejection. Peer pressure exert big influence on an individual, because of the fear of social rejection, individual is projected to follow the group rules including acts which may be damaging to their work-life and domestic relations such as gambling. The research finding builds upon revelations by Magoon and Ingersoll (2006) on social forces that impact the engagement in gambling. It was stated that increased parental monitoring was

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associated with lower levels of adolescent gambling. The findings of Orford et al (2009) that people with parents or relatives/peers who had experienced gambling-related problems are more likely to gamble also holds water here. It goes to accentuate that the gregarious nature of humans can affect actions undertaken by individuals.

Financial strain is defined as perceived economic stress and lack of economic support. It is described as inability to meet one's financial obligation (Adam, Meyers and Beidas 2017). Financial strain is associated with differs risk-taking behaviour and gambling. (Shaw, Agahi and Krause 2011) found financial strain as correlate of Alcohol use and smoking, (Odimeqwu 2017) reported that financial strain influences sexual risk behaviour, (Adam et al 2017) found a positive relationship between financial strain and poor academic performance. Financial strain or stress motivate or pushes youths to gambling (Okon 2015). Ironically financial strain is not just a motivating factor for gambling, it also serve as detrimental consequences (Ahaibwe 2016). Gambling can result in increased debt which can seem unsurmountable. The level of debt can be so high that gamblers may lose cars, job, savings or even the home to gambling (Kimberley, 2005; Turner, Preston, Saunders, McAvoy, and Jain, 2009).

Socioeconomic status (SES) is a combined total measure of a person's economic and social relative to others, based on income, education

and occupation Furthermore, when analyzing a family's SES, the household income earners, education and occupation are examined as well as combined income with an individual when their own attributes are assessed. Family income, occupational prestige, and educational attainments are measures of socio-economic status (SES) that have been found to influence an individual's gambling habit (Marmot and Michael, 2004). Low socioeconomic background has more gambling problems than other youth with high socioeconomic status (Welte, Barnes, Wiczorek, Tidwell, and Parker, 2001). Pathological gambling is characterized by an unequal socioeconomic distribution. Individuals from lower-income and ethnic minority groups and communities reported higher rates of pathological gambling than the general population (Marshall, 2005; Orford, Wardle, Griffiths, Sproston, and Erens, 2007; Volberg and Wray, 2007). Individuals with higher economic need, such as people who are poor compared with relevant others or victims of inequality, were more likely to engage in pathological gambling (Callan, Ellard, Shead, and Hodgins, 2008; Callan, Shead, and Olson, 2011). A recent meta-analysis has shown that gambling urges were strongly associated with personal relative deprivation, which refers to resentment stemming from the belief that one is deprived of a desired and deserved outcome compared to some referent (Callan, Shead, and Olson, 2015).

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The propensity to gamble is strongly influenced by personal income level. Study by McComb and Hanson (2009) showed that abstention from gambling amounted to an average of 65 percent among respondents in the highest two income categories compared to 78.5 percent among respondents in the poorest two categories. The abstention rate decreased as income increased. The lowest abstention rate was recorded in the middle-income category. No significant peculiarities are evident across the different income groups as far as participation in different gambling modes is concerned.

Residence has influences on gambling behavior and are important to understand because localities can control the sanction and location of gambling opportunities (e.g., lottery and slot machine venues are more common in disadvantaged neighborhoods as compared with more affluent neighborhoods). Individuals living in disadvantaged neighborhoods were more likely to report higher frequencies of gambling behaviors and gambling problems than those who did not live in disadvantaged neighborhoods (Barnes Welte and Tidwell 2011). A US national telephone survey found that neighborhood disadvantage showed no effect on past year gambling, but it had a strong positive effect on frequency of gambling and problem/pathological gambling. Those living in the 10 % most disadvantaged neighborhoods were 12 times more likely to have gambling problems as compared with the 10 % living in the least disadvantaged neighborhoods. In

another US national telephone survey, the mean number of days in the past year spent gambling were twice as high among participants who lived in the top fifth most disadvantaged neighborhoods as compared with those residing in neighborhoods of the lowest fifth disadvantage (Welte, Wieczorek and Barnes2004).

Welte et al (2004) suggest that compositional aspects of disadvantaged neighborhoods, such as being the subject of racial discrimination, being exposed to neighborhood violence, living in poverty, and having low social competence, promote gambling. Among adolescents from a Great Lakes Indian Reservation marked with great poverty, 48 % reported that they often “dreamt of solving their problems by winning a lot of money” and 33 % felt gambling was a “fast and easy way to earn money” (Pearce, Mason and Hiscock 2008). On the other hand, the proximity or physical access to gambling venues might be what links neighborhood disadvantage to gambling activities and problems. In Montreal, Canada, students attending high schools in lower socio-economic status neighborhoods (with a higher concentration of gambling venues) as compared with more affluent neighborhoods (where gambling venues are less common), are 40 % more likely to gamble (Wilson, Gilliland and Ross 2006). In Nevada, where there are three major casino markets as well as several Indian casinos, the prevalence of gambling problems was

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substantially higher than that of the national US estimate.

Statement of Problem

The rate at which youths are engaging in various forms of gambling is increasing daily. Hardly would one find any clusters of undergraduates that are not ruminating or getting involved in gambling activities in this current dispensation and this could be owned to certain factors. The time that are supposed to be invested into profitable and precious activities are wasted on argument and speculations on gambling results and related activities as observed by the researcher. Also, financial strain experienced by undergraduates could be a determining factor that precipitates gambling behaviours among students. This could be as a result of unemployment, bad governance, economy recession and lots other factors. So in order to survive, many undergraduates see gambling as a means to end. Gambling behaviour often results in behavioural, emotional, relationship, or financial problems which may develop into a diagnosable condition known as problem or pathological gambling if not properly handled. Also high availability and easy accessibility of various patterns of gambling render many undergraduates vulnerable to gambling. Consequently, as a result of onset and continued gambling, many undergraduate experience lack of income, loss of study hours, low academic performance, substance use and abuse, depression, maladjustment, frustration, stealing, and school dropout. Gambling has led

to many undergraduates joining criminal gang, being initiated into cultism. Hence the need for this study.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to investigate the factors influencing gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study intend to:

Investigate the influence of depression on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

Examine the influence of peer pressure on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

Ascertain the influence of income (high or low) on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

Determine the influence of residence (rural/urban) on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

To what extent does depression influence gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State?

To what extent does peer pressure influence gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State?

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To what extent does income (high or low) influence gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State?

To what extent does residence influence gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State?

Research Hypothesis

The following hypotheses are postulated to guide the researcher in the study. It will be tested at 0.05 alpha level.

There is no significant relationship between depression and gambling behavior among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

There is no significant relationship between peer pressure and gambling behavior among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

There is no significant difference between the influence income (high or low) and gambling behavior among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

There is no significant difference between the influence residence (Urban or Rural) and gambling behavior among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

Significance of the Study

This study will be of significance to educators' counselors, parents, ministry of education, University authority, and students and will add to the existing literature on gambling behaviour. The findings and recommendations will equip parents on how to understand when their children have been involved in gambling, and

how to help them come out of it. Also, it will help parents to understand does conditions that predispose their children to gambling and provide recommendations on ways to avoid it. If students' educators, decision-makers and school administrators understand factors that influence gambling behaviour, they will make policies that will prevent gambling in the university. If ministry of education known factors that predispose students to gambling, they will be able to develop curricular and educational interventions to minimize the rate at which students get involved in gambling in the academic environment. The findings and recommendations of this study will be significant to students. It will help them understand how gambling affects their academic life, social life, physical health and emotional health. To the counselors, the findings and recommendations of the study will help them to properly focus on the underlined causes of gambling and give proper guidance and counseling to student with gambling problem. The study would proffer solutions on how to reduce the rate of gambling among students and invariably reduce harmful effects that are caused by gambling among undergraduate students. This study will also add to the knowledge and existing literature on factors influence of gambling behaviour among undergraduate students.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The study is limited to fulltime undergraduate students in Rivers State. The study is limited to

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depression, peer pressure, income and residence as independent variable while gambling behaviour among undergraduate students is the dependent variable. Only fulltime undergraduate students are used as subjects in the course of the study. The study is also limited to tertiary universities in Rivers State

1.8 Area of the Study

The area for this study is Rivers State. Rivers State also known simply as Rivers is a state in the Niger Delta region of southern Nigeria. Formed in 1967, when it split from the former Eastern Region. Rivers State borders Imo and Abia States to the north, Akwa Ibom State to the east, and Bayelsa and Delta states to the west. The state capital, Port Harcourt, is a metropolis that is considered the commercial center of the Nigerian oil industry. Rivers state has twenty one (21) local government areas. With a population of 5,198,716 as of the 2006 census, Rivers State is the 6th most populous state in Nigeria. Rivers State is a diverse state that is home to many minority ethnic groups, including the Ogoni, Ikwerre, Ijaw, and Okrika people. The state is particularly noted for its linguistic diversity, with 28 indigenous languages being said to be spoken in Rivers State. Rivers State has a total area of 11,077 km² (4,277 sq mi), making it the 26th largest state by area. Rivers State has higher literacy rate compared to most states in the South South geopolitical zone. Its male literacy as of 2006 was 52.3% while female literacy rate was 47.7%. Rivers state is blessed

natural resources such as; crude oil, gas, silica sand, glass sand and clay. Prior to the discovery of oil in commercial quantity in 1951, Agriculture was the primary occupation of the people of Rivers State. Around the 19th century when the industrial revolution reached its peak in England, the area was then referred to as Oil Rivers Protectorate, this was due to its abundant palm oil and kernel which basically constituted the main revenue source of the country. In a sample survey carried out by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources, about 40% of the rural inhabitants were committed to farming in 1983. Rivers State is one of the leading states in the production of yam, cassava, cocoyam, maize, rice and beans.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

INTRODUCTION

This chapter deals with the following headings:

Conceptual Review

Theoretical Review

Empirical Review

Summary of Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Gambling

Gambling, wagering real money in order to win money is a social activity existing in almost all cultures and across development. A person is gambling whenever he or she takes the chance of losing money or belongings, and when winning or losing is decided mostly by chance. Gambling is a cultural, social and economic phenomenon that has pervaded most cultures in

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In general, two of the most useful definitions of gambling are the following: first “using real money for a variety of types of activities, including: purchasing lottery tickets, betting on sports pools, playing cards, playing bingo, playing slot machines, betting on video games or video poker, and betting on other games of skill.” (Gupta and Derevensky, 1996); second “an activity that implies an element of risk, and that money, or something of sentimental or monetary value, could be won or lost by the participants.” (Ladouceur, Boudreault, Jacques, and Vitaro 1999). Productivity commission (PC) (2010) define gambling as an exchange of wealth determined by a future event the outcome of which is unknown at the time of the wager. Gambling also is described as betting money or some form of property on the outcome of a game or event that is ultimately based on chance (Sammut 2010). Gambling therefore is a type of game in which financial loss or gain for the players is part of or even the main point of the results of the game.

The origins of gambling cannot be known for certain as it has been with mankind since pre historic times. Gambling and risk taking have been part of human culture since ancient times.

Early accounts of gambling apparatus date back many centuries, with ivory dice recovered from Egyptian tombs made sometime before 1500 B.C. The Chinese, Japanese, Greeks and Romans were also known to practice games of skill and chance for amusement as early as 2300 B.C. (American Gaming Association, (AGA) 2003). Other findings indicate that the oldest back- gammon set to have ever been discovered is thought to be five thousand years old, was found in modern day Iran, and is older than the one found in ancient Mesopotamia, considered being the cradle of civilization (Sammut 2010). Gambling seems to be so important to mankind since it has been around longer than civilization itself and is present in every society, it is postulated that the origin of gambling might have come from the practice of divination that is the casting of sticks, stones and bones as a means of communication with the gods or spirits. Sammut (2010) explains that man’s nature to question his surroundings and to seek meaning in existence provided the basis for religion as well as science; and his fascination with the random can easily be seen to have given rise to the charm of gambling. Also it is indicated that Native Americans, believed gods determined their luck and chance and developed games and language related to gambling.

Tertiary students have been identified as an at risk group in relation to gambling. Many students have increased freedom at this age and are frequent internet users and fall into the age

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that was done by Petry and Weinstock (2007), in an American university revealed that out of 1356 student participants, 23% reported ever gambling on the internet, 6.3% gambled online weekly and about a third of these online gamblers (who had ever gambled online) were classified as probable pathological gamblers. Studies have suggested that certain groups are more likely to be attracted to online gambling.

In Nigeria, gambling sports betting has swept the country like storm in that most people bet on a daily basis. Sports betting has recently gained great popularity and become the most promising of gambling business, especially when it comes to betting on international football with the prestigious English premier league gaining the most attention. In Nigeria the sports betting has grown since 2007 when the first online sports betting company nairabet was registered. Other companies that have since been registered include: Bet9ja, Betway, merrybet, bet360, betking, saharabet, etc. There are also lottery such as lotto, charity sweepstake, etc. which are very popular and are advertised widely in mass media. Nigerian players have enjoyed online and mobile sports betting while most of the operators offer services in the country through betting shops or by adopting the new trend that uses mobile and online platforms.

This new trend of betting among the people of many communities has been explained in many ways. Sammut (2010) indicates that many communities, often those suffering economic

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hardship and social problems, consider gambling as a panacea to those ills. Indeed, a number of communities plagued by high unemployment have found a form of economic renewal through gambling, particularly through the development of casinos and betting centers. The youth especially university students have resulted into betting and at times they do it at the expense of education. In several instances university students have committed suicide after losing on bets, some have failed to do exams and even totally failed to continue with university education because they used the money that was meant for fee to bet and lost. Before now, gambling had not been a problem in Nigeria universities in the 80's and 90's it has become a serious problem in the recent years which calls for research and understanding. Although problem gambling exists in all age categories, college students are a particularly vulnerable group, as going to college often represents the first move away from a student's family with fewer associated restrictions on their activities (Shaffer et al 2005). Researchers report this segment of the population as having three times the rate of "disordered" gambling than that of adults from the general population (Gose, 2000) and among the highest frequency of problem and pathological gambling of any segment of the population (Shaffer, et al 1991). It is established that about 67% of all college students bet on sports (Weinstock et al 2007). Hence this problem on student involvement in gambling

should not be overlooked since it has adverse effects on student behavior and the society as a whole and has become a nationwide concern in Nigeria.

2.1.2 Concept Depression and Gambling Behaviour

According to Colman (2003) depression is a state of sadness, gloom, and pessimistic ideation, with loss of interest or pleasure in normally enjoyable activities, accompanied in severe cases by anorexia and consequent weight loss. Depression manifests as deep sorrow or grief, insomnia, loss of appetite, unpleasant mood, hopelessness, irritability, self-dislike, and suicidal tendencies. It has been observed that when gamblers lose a bet, they show signs of depression and some have been reported to have committed suicide because of loss of bet. Gambling problems tend to co-occur with other mental disorders. Data from the population-based United States National Comorbidity Survey Replication (NCS-R) indicated that 96 % of respondents with lifetime pathological gambling also met diagnostic criteria for at least one other psychiatric disorder (Kessler, Hwang, LaBrie, Petukhova, Sampson, and Winters 2008). Major depression is one of the most common disorders that co-occur with problem gambling. The rate of comorbidity between lifetime pathological gambling and depression in the NCS-R was 39 % (Kessler et al. 2008). Data from another large population-based

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sample from the United States indicated a similar comorbidity rate between lifetime pathological gambling and major depression of 37 % (Petry, Stinson, and Grant, 2005). A recent meta-analysis reported an average prevalence rate of 23 % for comorbid major depression among problem and pathological gamblers from general population samples, combining current and lifetime estimates of the disorders (Lorains, Cowlshaw, and Thomas 2011).

There is some preliminary evidence that the presence of significant depressive symptoms may exacerbate the severity and worsen the prognosis of problem gambling. Thomsen, Callesen, Linnet, Kringelbach and Moller (2009) found that pathological gamblers with higher levels of depressive symptoms exhibited more severe gambling behavior compared to those low in depressive symptoms, in the form of increased urges to gamble and greater duration of gambling during in-laboratory slot machine play. In a study of pathological gamblers who recently quit gambling, comorbid lifetime depression predicted a longer time to achieve stable abstinence from gambling (Hodgins, Peden, and Cassidy 2005) and negative affect was a commonly cited precipitant to relapse (Hodgins and el-Guebaly 2004). Thus, these studies suggest that depression may be associated with more severe gambling symptomatology among problem gamblers.

The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th Edition (DSM-5) recognizes

gambling disorder in the diagnostic category of substance-related and addictive disorders (APA 2013). Gambling disorder is defined by persistent and uncontrolled gambling, despite serious personal and social consequences (APA 2013). Prior to DSM-5, the behavior characteristic of gambling disorder was referred to as pathological gambling (APA 2000), and thus much research has been conducted on the phenomenon of pathological gambling. In the gambling literature, problem gambling is a more general term used to describe gambling activity that leads to harm to the individual, his or her family, and/or others in his or her social network or community (Ferris et al. 1999). Problem gambling includes pathological gambling/gambling disorder as well as harmful gambling behavior that do not necessarily meet DSM diagnostic criteria for pathological gambling (Raylu and Oei 2002).

Comorbid depression may also influence motivations for gambling. Studies of problem gamblers have found that a substantial proportion report gambling to escape from negative emotions or problems and/or to increase positive affect (Wood and Griffiths 2007). Given the centrality of negative affect to major depression, problem gamblers who are depressed may be more likely than those who are not depressed to use gambling to reduce negative feelings. Along this line, Blaszczynski and Nower (2002) proposed a conceptual pathways model of problem gambling which delineates three distinct subtypes of problem

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gamblers, one of which is emotionally vulnerable gamblers. According to the pathways model, emotionally vulnerable problem gamblers have comorbid emotional problems such as depression and anxiety and are motivated to gamble initially to improve their mood or escape from negative emotions or problems.

The pathways model (Blaszczynski and Nower 2002) provides a framework for conceptualizing other important variables that may distinguish depressed from non-depressed problem gamblers. Blaszczynski and Nower (2002) suggested that emotionally vulnerable problem gamblers are more likely to present with problematic family backgrounds, adverse childhood experiences, and life stress. They hypothesized that these risk factors as well as certain personality traits produce emotional vulnerability that can lead to problem gambling in conjunction with other biological vulnerabilities and ecological factors. Thus, from this theoretical perspective, problem gamblers with comorbid depression may differ from those without depression in terms of their family functioning, history of childhood trauma and abuse, and personality profile. While no studies have yet examined these factors in individuals with comorbid problem gambling and depression, there is some research on these factors in the contexts of problem gambling and depression separately.

A small number of studies have found that treatment-seeking problem gamblers report

greater family dysfunction (Dowling et al. 2009). According to these studies, treatment-seeking problem gamblers perceive their family members to be less supportive and committed, less assertive and self-sufficient, less likely to emphasize achievement or competition, and less likely to have intellectual or cultural interests, compared to a normative standardization sample (Dowling et al. 2009). Depression has also been found to impair family functioning (Moos and Moos 2009). Parental depression is correlated with higher levels of conflict and use of psychological control (e.g., intrusiveness, control through guilt) and lower levels of parental warmth (Cummings et al. 2005).

Given that both problem gambling and depression have shown associations with poorer family functioning independently, family dysfunction may be particularly associated with comorbid problem gambling and depression.

Studies have reported elevated rates of childhood abuse and trauma among problem gamblers seeking treatment, with higher rates for female gamblers (Ciarrocchi and Richardson 1989). Childhood maltreatment has predicted greater severity and frequency of gambling in both treatment-seeking and community samples of gamblers (Hodgins et al. 2010). However, it is unclear whether relationships observed between childhood trauma and gambling in these studies may have been influenced by comorbid conditions, including depression. Childhood trauma is also a strong risk factor for the development of depression

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(Heim et al. 2008). Severity of childhood abuse has been linked to earlier age of onset of depression and greater chronicity of depression (Bernet and Stein 1999). Given these associations, childhood trauma may be a particularly important factor for the development of comorbid problem gambling and depression.

Personality factors have also been demonstrated to predict both problem gambling and depression (King et al. 2010). A recent meta-analysis suggests that the personality profile of problem gamblers is characterized by high negative affect, low conscientiousness, and disinhibition (MacLaren et al. 2011). Evidence indicates that depression is linked to the personality traits of high neuroticism/negative emotionality, low extraversion/positive emotionality, and low conscientiousness (Kotov et al. 2010). Comorbid depression may affect the personality profile of problem gambling, with implications for theories of the etiology of comorbid problem gambling and depression.

2.1.3 Concept of Peer Pressure and Gambling Behaviour

Peer pressure" can be described as the influence exerted by a peer group in encouraging a person to change his or her attitudes, values, or behaviours to conform to the group. According to Abdulbaqi, Tejideen, and Andajisegbede (2019) stated that there is significant relationship between peer influence and engagement in gambling. A person that is associated with friend that participates in

gambling is also vulnerable to gambling related activities. This can be justified based on the fact that an individual who fails to conform to group norms may face social rejection. Peer pressure exert big influence on an individual, because of the fear of social rejection, individual is projected to follow the group rules including acts which may be damaging to their work-life and domestic relations such as gambling. The research finding builds upon revelations by Magoon and Ingersoll (2006) on social forces that impact the engagement in gambling. It was stated that increased parental monitoring was associated with lower levels of adolescent gambling. The findings of Orford et al (2009) that people with parents or relatives/peers who had experienced gambling-related problems are more likely to gamble also holds water here. It goes to accentuate that the gregarious nature of humans can affect actions undertaken by individuals.

Gambling more is associated with peer conflict and lower family cohesion (Ladouceur and Mireault, 2005), a family history of gambling and interacting with peers who gamble and with reporting more positive parental and peer attitudes toward gambling. Wickwire et al. (2008) found that peer disapproval was negatively related to gambling among adolescents and female students but positively related to gambling among male students. Studies have found that not only do many peer believe that gambling is a harmless activity (Volberg et al., 2008), young people's gambling

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is facilitated by their peer group. For example, Fabiansson (2008) reported that the majority of her participants were introduced to gambling by their peers. Gambling problems among young people appear to be related to peer gambling (Wickwire et al., 2008). Similarly, problem gamblers are more interested in gambling than non-problem gamblers if their first gambling experience was with their peers (Splevins et al., 2010).

Two studies have considered the role of perceived social norms as predictors of gambling behaviour among college students. Larimer and Neighbors (2003) found that both the perceived descriptive and injunctive norms of other students were predictors of gambling frequency, expenditure, and consequences and problem gambling, measured. However, Neighbors et al. (2007) found that positive attitudes toward gambling were positively related to problematic gambling as were the perceived approval of friends. However, inconsistent with the perceived approval of other students was negatively related. One reason for these discrepant findings is that Larimer and Neighbors did not include attitudes in their study and only measured perceived gambling norms for other students whereas Neighbors et al. included the perceived norms of peer, friends, and other students.

2.1.4 Concept of Income and Gambling Behaviour

The propensity to gamble is strongly influenced by personal income level. Study by McComb

and Hanson (2009) showed that abstention from gambling amounted to an average of 65 percent among respondents in the highest two income categories compared to 78.5 percent among respondents in the poorest two categories. The abstention rate decreased as income increased. The lowest abstention rate was recorded in the middle-income category. No significant peculiarities are evident across the different income groups as far as participation in different gambling modes is concerned.

Socioeconomic status (SES) is a combined total measure of a person's economic and social relative to others, based on income, education and occupation. Furthermore, when analyzing a family's SES, the household income earners, education and occupation are examined as well as combined income with an individual when their own attributes are assessed. Family income, occupational prestige, and educational attainments are measures of socio-economic status (SES) that have been found to influence an individual's gambling habit (Marmot and Michael, 2004). Low socioeconomic background has more gambling problems than other youth with high socioeconomic status (Welte, Barnes, Wiczorek, Tidwell, and Parker, 2001).

Pathological gambling is characterized by an unequal socioeconomic distribution. Individuals from lower-income and ethnic minority groups and communities reported higher rates of pathological gambling than the general population (Marshall, 2005; Orford, Wardle,

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Griffiths, Sproston, and Erens, 2007; Volberg and Wray, 2007). Individuals with higher economic need, such as people who are poor compared with relevant others or victims of inequality, were more likely to engage in pathological gambling (Callan, Ellard, Shead, and Hodgins, 2008; Callan, Shead, and Olson, 2011). A recent meta-analysis has shown that gambling urges were strongly associated with personal relative deprivation, which refers to resentment stemming from the belief that one is deprived of a desired and deserved outcome compared to some referent (Callan, Shead, and Olson, 2015).

2.1.5 Concept of Residence and Gambling Behaviour

Residence influences on gambling behavior are important to understand because localities can control the sanction and location of gambling opportunities (e.g., lottery and slot machine venues are more common in disadvantaged neighborhoods as compared with more affluent neighborhoods). Individuals living in disadvantaged neighborhoods were more likely to report higher frequencies of gambling behaviors and gambling problems than those who did not live in disadvantaged neighborhoods (Barnes Welte and Tidwell 2011). A US national telephone survey found that neighborhood disadvantage showed no effect on past year gambling, but it had a strong positive effect on frequency of gambling and problem/pathological gambling. Those living in the 10 % most disadvantaged neighborhoods

were 12 times more likely to have gambling problems as compared with the 10 % living in the least disadvantaged neighborhoods. In another US national telephone survey, the mean number of days in the past year spent gambling were twice as high among participants who lived in the top fifth most disadvantaged neighborhoods as compared with those residing in neighborhoods of the lowest fifth disadvantage (Welte, Wieczorek and Barnes2004).

Welte et al (2004) suggest that compositional aspects of disadvantaged neighborhoods, such as being the subject of racial discrimination, being exposed to neighborhood violence, living in poverty, and having low social competence, promote gambling. Among adolescents from a Great Lakes Indian Reservation marked with great poverty, 48 % reported that they often “dreamt of solving their problems by winning a lot of money” and 33 % felt gambling was a “fast and easy way to earn money” (Pearce, Mason and Hiscock 2008). On the other hand, the proximity or physical access to gambling venues might be what links neighborhood disadvantage to gambling activities and problems. In Montreal, Canada, students attending high schools in lower socio-economic status neighborhoods (with a higher concentration of gambling venues) as compared with more affluent neighborhoods (where gambling venues are less common), are 40 % more likely to gamble (Wilson, Gilliland and Ross 2006). In Nevada, where there are three major casino

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markets as well as several Indian casinos, the prevalence of gambling problems was substantially higher than that of the national US estimate.

As distance from one's home to various gambling opportunities (i.e., casinos, video lottery/slot machine venues, racetrack, and places that sell lottery tickets) were collected from past-year gamblers only, the relationships between gambling proximity with gambling frequency and gambling problems were next assessed among the respondents that gambled in the past-year. Nine percent of the past-year gamblers lived within a 1-h drive from the nearest casino (Figure 1), 65.5 % from the nearest video lottery/slot machine venues, 72.1 % from the nearest racetrack, and 90.9 % from the nearest place that sells lottery tickets. While the differences were not statistically significant, the results showed a general trend for frequent gamblers and gamblers with any gambling problems to be more likely to live closer to video lottery/slot machine venues, racetrack, and places that sell lottery tickets than infrequent gamblers and gamblers with no gambling problems, respectively.

2.2 Theoretical Review

This study was anchored on the following theories: Social Learning Theory, Personality theory of gambling and integrated models.

2.2.1 Social Learning Theory

This study is anchored on social learning theory. Social Learning Theory- advanced by Albert Bandura (1977), the theory suggests that people

can learn a behavior merely by observing the behaviours of others. The social learning model of gambling proposes that gambling as a form of behavior that is highly subjected to reinforcement and reward. the theory propose that as individual engage in gambling and such gambling brings high return in term of money, such individual is motivated and reinforce to participate more in the is behaviour. This reinforcement tends to strengthen the relationship between gambling and outcome of such gambling (reward). The theory posits that this reinforcement create a sense of physiological arousal which serves as motivation or enforcement for an individual to engage in gambling in other to gain more profit. In other words, as level for return from gambling is encouraging, such individual are engage more in gambling and may eventually experience gambling addiction at the end. The theory suggests a strong association between reward and gambling predisposes individual in more gambling related activities. Meanwhile Skinner (1953) justifies the claim above when he claimed that the level of individual participation in gambling related activities is a function of reinforcement history. The reinforcement history can be explained base on the fact that whether such individual has been making profit from gambling or not. In other word the level of success in the previous gambling go along way on predicting whether such individual will engage more in gambling at future time.

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Further, Custer (1982) also explained that early big reward or win from gambling predisposes individual to gambling in future tome. Win serves as motivation which improve individual attitude toward gambling. However, in the case of problem gambling where people still engage in gambling without despite the fact that they are losing, the explanation for this is based on the fact that the first reward from gambling create a great and very strong reinforcement which last long till the person get addicted to gambling. From the social learning theory explanation, Brown (1987) suggest that there are six major mechanism which predisposes people to gambling addiction; they are

- i. Felling of anxiety or depression
- ii. Cognitive distortion concerning gambling behaviour
- iii. Reinforcement schedule
- iv. Opportunity and availability of gambling spot
- v. Attitude of socio-cultural context toward gambling
- vi. Internal relationship

Furthermore, Brown (1987) reiterated that an individual is predisposes to gambling if he/she is residing in a culture which permit gambling and the attitude of the people toward gambling is positive. In other word, an individual living in an environment where people are engaging in gambling, such individual is also expected to join the group and participate in such act. Brown (1987) also suggests that physiological arousal also motivate an individual to engage in

gambling, Brown claim that internal reinforcement improve the vulnerability of individual to gambling. The internal urge to gamble according to Brown predisposes individual to engage in gambling. Gambling availability in Nigeria according to this theory is one of the reasons while some people may experience gambling and eventually develop a gambling addiction.

2.2.2 Personality theory

There is no typical personality profile found among problem or pathological gamblers. A number of studies have found elevated scores on some personality traits, such as impulsivity, with inconsistent findings on others, such as sensation seeking (Raylu and Oei, 2002). There is no consistent finding in relation to extraversion, neuroticism and locus of control. However, while no personality profile exists, specific traits, particularly impulsivity, sensation-seeking and propensity for risk taking, may be important variables moderating or modulating gambling behaviour and acting as risk factors in the aetiology of pathological gambling.

Although existing studies have reported high rates of Axis II personality disorders among populations of pathological gamblers in treatment (Specker, Carlson, Edmonson, Johnson, and Marcotte, 1996) and in the community (Desai and Potenza, 2008), particularly those falling within the Cluster B category (narcissistic, antisocial and borderline), there are no coherent or unique

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patterns emerging. In addition, some anti-social features may develop as a result of the stresses caused by gambling-related problems and the strategies used to conceal these from others.

2.2.3 Integrated models

In response to the multiplicity of environmental, familial, and intrapsychic variables identified, several integrated explanatory models have been advanced. Early theorists such as Jacobs (1986) and Brown (1997) offered more general theories of addiction that also encompassed gambling. These focused on the two-factor processes of maintenance of hedonic tone or optimal/homeostatic levels of arousal, the role of personality traits, and psychological predisposition to feelings of inadequacy, self-esteem and self-efficacy. Excitement/arousal produced positive hedonic tone while dissociation and narrowing of attention underpinned emotional escape. Substantial evidence exists that gambling produces dissociation (Diskin and Hodgins, 2003).

Reformulating her earlier biopsychosocial model (Sharpe and TARRIER, 1993), Sharpe (2002) proposed a descriptive stress-diathesis model that attempted to take into consideration all of the following: predisposing genetic and biological vulnerabilities; environmental influences setting the foundation for attitudes toward, and exposure to, gambling; peer group interactions; early gambling win/loss experiences; and, the interactive role of arousal (conditioning), cognitive biases and coping

strategies. Blaszczynski and Nower (2002) based their integrated model on the assumption that pathological gamblers represented a heterogeneous group that could be sub-typed according to underlying motivation and benefits derived from gambling. The model identifies three primary subgroups or clusters of gamblers: behaviourally conditioned, emotionally vulnerable, and biologically-based impulsive. It is assumed that all subtypes manifest similar symptoms and signs but that there are important differences in the pathogenesis of the disorder. Similar to Sharpe (2002), the model accepts the relevance of environmental factors in shaping early attitudes toward gambling, and the central role of arousal, conditioning and cognitive distortions as variables are common to all three subtypes. However, the point of departure from Sharpe's model is in the importance placed on additional factors that discriminate subtypes. For the behaviourally conditioned subgroup, conditioning and cognitive processes are of primary aetiological significance. For the emotionally vulnerable, affective disturbances, poor coping skills, dealing with painful emotional experiences, social isolation, and low self-esteem, efficacy and image act to exacerbate the effect of the conditioning and cognitive processes. Under these circumstances, emotional escape plays a major motivational role. For the biologically-based impulsive gamblers, genetic and neurochemical factors

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contribute to impulsivity and need for stimulation.

Empirical evidence supporting Blaszczynski and Nower's (2002) model is emerging. For example, Ledgerwood and Petry (2006) and Stewart, Zack, Collins, Klein, and Fragopoulos (2008) reported that principal components analysis supported a three factor solution consistent with normal, emotionally vulnerable, and biologically based subgroups. However, further research is required to refine and obtain empirical data confirming the validity and reliability of subtypes within each pathway.

In summary, no single or integrated model of gambling is able to explain the causal factors responsible for the development of pathological gambling. However, integrated models taking into account the multifactorial biopsychosocial variables appear to be gaining prominence.

2.3 Empirical Review

Annie, Sean and Sherry (2016) symptoms of depression and problem gambling across 4 waves and addresses whether their relation is directional (with one reliably preceding the other), bidirectional, or pathoplastic. As part of the Manitoba Longitudinal Study of Young Adults, prospective data were collected on Canadian young adults' (Wave 1: n¹/4679, 51.8%female, aged 18 to 20 years) depressive symptoms, involvement in gambling, and risky gambling behaviour. Recruitment and the first cycle of data collection (Wave 1) took place in fall 2007. Three additional waves of data collection then occurred in 12- to 18-month

intervals: fall 2008, spring 2010, and spring 2011. The Problem Gambling Severity Index and the Composite International Diagnostic Interview—Short Form were administered through telephone interview at each wave. Bivariate growth curves showed that depressive and problem gambling symptoms were positively correlated at Wave 1, Wave 2, and Wave 4. Neither disorder was found to be a risk factor for the other, and depression and problem gambling were not pathoplastically related (that is, increases in one did not result in increases in the other over time, and vice versa). While depression and problem gambling are related, their co-occurrence may be better explained not by depressive- or gambling-related risk, but by the presence of a common underlying factor (such as substance abuse).

Bankole, Adebunmi and Bankole (2019) investigate personality characteristics and financial strain as a determinant of gambling behaviour among youth in Nigeria. Three instruments were used in the study which include Gambling behaviour scale developed by Jeffery (2010) used in measuring prevalence and pattern of gambling behaviour, Big five personality scale developed by Goldberg (1993) used in assessing personality domain of an individual and Financial strain scale developed by Aldana and Liljenquist (1998) used in measuring the rate of financial strain experienced by people. Three hundred and twenty participants (320) were used in this study but two hundred and ninety seven

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participants (297) responses were retrieved for analysis. Hypotheses were tested using regression analysis and independent t-test and the result were discussed according to literatures. It was concluded from the study that personality characteristics and financial strain predicts gambling behaviour and also there is sex differences in gambling behaviour. As a result of this, it was however recommended that youths are to be trained on how to improve their behavioural attitudes and should be well guided so as to avoid gambling because it has serious effects on their psychological health and overall well-being.

Jessica, Peter and Denise (2016) investigated influence of parental and peer problem gambling predicted emerging adult problem gambling, and whether reduced gambling self-stigma mediated these relationships. A community sample of 188 Australian gamblers aged 18 to 29 ($M = 21.41$, $SD = 2.99$) completed three versions of the Problem Gambling Severity Index (PGSI) and the Gambling Perception Scale. Results indicated that perceived parental and peer gambling were positively related to emerging adult problem gambling. While reduced gambling helping stigma was related to higher problem gambling, stigma did not mediate the links between significant others' gambling and emerging adult problem gambling. The study conclude that social influences are important in the development of problem gambling for young people, and that older male emerging adults

who have a gambling mother are at most risk of problem gambling.

Silvia, Carla, Grace and Nicholas (2012) explores whether neighborhood disadvantage is associated with gambling among predominantly low-income, urban young adults and to explore if there is differences in physical vs. compositional aspects of the neighborhood. Data are from a sample of 596 young adults interviewed when they were 21–22 years, who have been participating in a longitudinal study since entering first grade in nine public US Mid-Atlantic inner-city schools (88 % African Americans). Data were analyzed via factor analysis and logistic regression models. One third of the sample ($n=187$) were past-year gamblers, 42 % of them gambled more than once a week, and 31 % had gambling-related problems. Those living in moderate and high disadvantaged neighborhoods were significantly more likely to be past-year gamblers than those living in low disadvantaged neighborhoods. Those living in high disadvantaged neighborhoods were ten times more likely than those living in low disadvantaged neighborhoods to have gambling problems. Factor analysis yielded a 2-factor model, an “inhabitant disadvantage factor” and a “surroundings disadvantage factor.” Nearly 60 % of the sample lived in neighborhoods with high inhabitants disadvantage ($n=375$) or high surroundings disadvantage ($n=356$). High inhabitants disadvantage was associated with past-year frequent gambling (odds ratios

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(aOR)=2.26 (1.01, 5.02)) and gambling problems (aOR=2.81 (1.18, 6.69)). Higher neighborhood disadvantage, particularly aspects of the neighborhood concerning the inhabitants, was associated with gambling frequency and problems among young adult gamblers from an urban, low-income setting.

Karl and Supa (2014) investigate gambling behaviour and psychosocial correlates among university students from 23 low and middle income and emerging economy countries. Using anonymous questionnaires, data were collected from 17789 university students, 41.7% men and 58.3% women, with a mean age of 20.9 years (SD=2.9), from 23 countries across Africa, Asia and Americas. Overall, 27.1% reported gambling less than once a week and 8.4% once a week or more; 13.9% in men and 4.4% in women. Multivariate logistic regression found that male gender, residing in a low or lower middle income country, having been in a physical fight, tobacco use, not always driving within the speed limit, sexual risk behaviour, depression and PTSD symptoms were associated with frequent gambling. Several clustering risk behaviours were identified which can be utilized gambling prevention approaches.

Quigley, Yakovenko, Hodgins, Dobson, Casey and Currie (2014) examined the prevalence of current major depression among problem gamblers (N = 105) identified from a community sample of men and women in Alberta, and examined group differences in gambling severity, escape motivation for

gambling, family functioning, childhood trauma, and personality traits across problem gamblers with and without comorbid depression. The prevalence of major depression among the sample of problem gamblers was 32.4 %. Compared to problem gamblers without depression (n = 71), problem gamblers with comorbid depression (n = 34) reported more severe gambling problems, greater history of childhood abuse and neglect, poorer family functioning, higher levels of neuroticism, and lower levels of extraversion, agreeableness, and conscientiousness. Furthermore, the problem gamblers with comorbid depression had greater levels of childhood abuse and neglect, worse family functioning, higher neuroticism, and lower agreeableness and conscientiousness than a comparison sample of recreational gamblers with depression (n = 160). These findings underscore the need to address comorbid depression in assessment and treatment of problem gambling and for continued research on how problem gambling is related to frequently co-occurring disorders such as depression.

2.4 Summary of Related Literature

This chapter actually concentrated on review of literature of past researchers, write ups and scholars opinions on factors influence of gambling behaviour among undergraduate students. Its aim is to expose the researcher and prospective readers, to various factors influencing gambling, its types and how it affect undergraduate students in Universities. The

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review of literature was carried out according to the sub variables of the study which are depression and gambling behaviour, peer pressure and gambling behaviour, income and gambling behaviour, and residence and gambling behaviour.

The view makes us aware that gambling is “wagering money or something of material value on an event with an uncertain outcome with the primary intent of winning additional money and/or material goods”. The study is anchored on social Learning Theory- advanced by Albert Bandura (1977). Social Learning Theory (SLT) asserts that a student involvement with gambling because role model is likely to have three consequential effects beginning with observation and imitation of gambling behavior followed by social reinforcement (encouragement) for early gamblers.

However, the researcher has discovered that most of the works that was carried out on factors influencing gambling behaviour have not been on social Learning Theory. This study differs from other study in terms of geographical area, population and sample size. From the researcher’s observation, no study has been conducted on the factors influencing gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The chapter presents the methodology, used in gathering data for this research. The chapter presents the method, used in gathering data for

this research. This chapter discusses the research design, population of the study, sample and sampling techniques, instrument for data collection, validity of the instruments, reliability of the instruments, administration of Instrument and finally method of data analysis.

3.1 Research Design

The research design used in this study is description survey which seeks to study the situations and conditions, as they exist. A survey research is a form of description research that is aimed at collecting large and small samples information from populations in order to examine the distribution, incidence and interaction of educational and sociological phenomena (Denga and Ali 1998). The method is appropriate, as there is no manipulating of variables neither is it possible to arrange for events to happen because they have already taken place.

3.2 Population of Study

The population of the study comprise of fulltime undergraduate student in tertiary university in Rivers State. The population of fulltime undergraduate students in Tertiary University in Rivers State is approximately 72,700 for fulltime. The undergraduate students of tertiary university in Rivers State are suitable for this study because of high rate of gambling among the students. The students of tertiary university in Rivers State have high rate of gambling activities going on within and outside the campus, which have attracted a lot of students to gambling in the campus. Within the rural and

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urban areas, there is more than three bet shop within every street in Rivers State. With smart-phone, online betting is also popular among tertiary Students in Rivers State.

3.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

A total of 300 respondents was randomly drawn from fulltime undergraduate students in tertiary universities in Rivers State as sample for the study. A convenient of three hundred (300) respondents made up of male and female. The samples was selected through systematic sampling technique. Total 100 respondents was drawn from each of the three tertiary universities in Rivers State.

3.4 Instruments for Data Collection

The instruments that were used for data collection is questionnaires titled; “Factors Influencing Gambling Behavior among Undergraduate Students, comprises of three (3) sub-scales namely; Depression Scale (DS), Gambling Behaviour scale (GBS) Peer Pressure scale (PPS). The questionnaire was used to collect data from undergraduate students. The instrument is made up to two sections, section A deals with Demographic inventory such as income level (increase/decrease) and Resident (rural/urban). Section B contains 5 items on depression scale (DPS), Section C contains on 5 items peer pressure scale (PPS) and Section D contains 15 items on gambling behaviour scale (GBS). The 4 point likert scale response was used. As noted earlier, the response pattern is

structured on the 4 points Likert scale of (SA) strongly agree, (A) agree, (D) disagree and (SD) strongly disagree .SA= 4, A= 3, D= 2, SD =1, the reverse was adopted for negatively stated items. Which were used to determine the opinion of respondents on factors influencing gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

3.5 Validity of Instrument

After developing the instrument; a copy were given to the project supervisor and other experts in the area of education, for assessment and for correction. Their corrections were made to modify the instruments before administration. This basis of validation of the instrument is face and content validity.

3.6 Reliability of the Instrument

To determine the reliability of the instruments, test-retest method was used. Twenty copies of questionnaire was administered to twenty respondents who is not part of the study, nor in the study area. After two weeks, the same instrument was administered to the same pilot group. The two sets of questionnaire were correlated. The joint calculated coefficient was 0.76 which indicate that there was high degree of consistency. But independently depression scale (DPS) has a coefficient of 0.57, peer pressure scale (PPS) has a reliability coefficient of 0.72, and gambling behaviour scale (GBS) has a reliability coefficient of 0.76

3.7 Method of Data Collection

The questionnaire was personally administered by the researcher in the tertiary universities in

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Rivers State, with the help of two research assistance. In other for this to be well achieved, the researcher took some time to explain to the students on how to fill the questionnaire and also explained the instrument to them, and the instrument was collected immediately from the students after completion.

3.8 Method of Data Analyses

Data was analyzed using simple regression to answer research question 1 and 2 and test hypotheses 1 and 2 while research question 3 and 4 and hypotheses 3 and 4 was tested using independent t-test and presented in a single table.

Table 4.1: Regression Analysis of the relationship between depression and gambling behavior among undergraduate students in Rivers State

R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Std error	Untand B		
0.917	0.840	0.840	0.488	.942		
Sum Sq	df	Summary Mean Sq.	F	α	Sig.	Remark
Regression	373.074	1	373.074			Ho
Residual	70.963	298	.238	1566.685	0.05	0.000 Rejected
Total	444.037	299				

*P < 0.05, df = 2, 298.

From the analyses in table 4.1, R= 0.917, R²= 0.840 adjusted R²= 0.840, standard error= 0.48799 while unstandard B=0.942. From the R² value, it means that depression accounts for 84% (0.840×100) of gambling behaviour among undergraduates in Rivers State. The unstandard B value showed that for every increase or decrease in the values of depression, there will be a corresponding 0.942 increases or decrease in the value of gambling behaviour.

**CHAPTER FOUR
PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND
DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS**

In this chapter, the results of data analysis, summary of findings and the discussion of finding are presented. Each hypothesis is reproduced and then pertinent table of results is displayed. The inference apparent from the table is then justified and drawn.

4.1 Presentation of Data Analysis

Research Question One: To what extent does depression influence gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State?

Calculated F= 1566.685 while significant value = 0.000. Hence, since significant value (P=0.000<0.05) at 298 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relation between depression and gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: To what extent does peer pressure influence gambling

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behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State?

Table 4.2: Regression Analysis of the relationship between peer pressure influences gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State

R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Std error	Untand B		
0.942	0.887	0.887	0.409	.943		
Sum Sq	df	Summary Mean Sq.	F	α	Sig.	Remark
Regression	394.053	2	394.053			Ho
Residual	49.984	298	.168	2349.321	0.05	0.000 Rejected
Total	444.037	299				

*P < 0.05, df = 2, 298.

From the analyses in table 4.2, R= 0.942, R²= 0.887 adjusted R²= 0.887, standard error= 0.40955 while unstandard B=0.934. From the R² value, it means that peer pressure accounts for 88.7% (0.887×100) of gambling behaviour among undergraduates in Rivers State. The unstandard B value showed that for every increase or decrease in the values of peer pressure, there will be a corresponding 0.934 increases or decrease in the value of gambling behaviour. Calculated F= 2349.321 while significant value = 0.000. Hence, since

Variables	N	X	SD	df	t	P-value
Low income	154	42.16	11.19	298	88.95	0.000
High income	146	38.55	10.99			

*P < 0.05, df = 298.

Table 4.3, shows that low income with gambling behaviour has a mean of 42.16 and standard deviation of 11.19 while high income with gambling behaviour has a mean of 38.55 and standard deviation of 10.99. This shows that low income had a higher mean than high

significant value (P=0.000<0.05) at 298 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relation between peer pressure and gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

Research Question Three: To what extent does income level influence gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State?

Research hypothesis 3 is answered with mean, standard deviation and independent sample t-test and the result is presented in table 4.3

income. So there is a significant difference in the influence of income on gambling behaviour as low income influence is higher. To test the null hypothesis, there is no significant influence of income on gambling behaviour. T-value was 88.95 and when it was tested at 0.05, the p-

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value of 0.00 was gotten, and this value is less than 0.005. The null hypothesis was rejected. The alternate hypothesis is therefore retained.

Research Question Four: To what extent does residence influence gambling

Variables	N	X	SD	df
Rural location	133	40.09	10.28	298
Urban location	167	39.00	11.82	

*P < 0.05, df = 298.

Table 4.4 shows that rural location with gambling behaviour has a mean of 40.09 and standard deviation of 10.28, while urban location with gambling behaviour has a mean of 39.00 and standard deviation of 11.82. This shows that rural location had a higher mean than urban location. So there is a significant difference in the influence of location on gambling behaviour as rural location influence is higher. To test the null hypothesis, there is no significant influence of location on gambling behaviour. T-value was 98.62 and when it was tested at 0.05, the p-value of 0.00 was gotten, and this value is less than 0.005. The null hypothesis was rejected. The alternate hypothesis is therefore retained.

4.2 Summary of Findings

From the analysis in the respective tables, the researchers found out that;

Depression has an influence on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

Peer pressure has an influence on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State?

Research hypothesis 4 is answered with mean, standard deviation and independent sample t-test and the result is presented in table 4.4

t	P-value
98.62	0.000

Income level has an influence on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

Location has an influence on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

4.3 Discussion of Finding

The result of hypothesis one indicates that depression has an influence on gambling behaviour. This means that people feel depressed after losing bet or placing a bet in anticipation of the bet outcome. It has also been noticed, from the result of the analysis, that people with depression gamble more. This is in line with the finding of Kessler et al (2008) who stated that gambling problems tend to co-occur with other mental disorders. Data from the population-based United States National Comorbidity Survey Replication (NCS-R) indicated that 96 % of respondents with lifetime pathological gambling also met diagnostic criteria for at least one other psychiatric disorder. This study also agrees with that of Thomsen et al (2009) who found that pathological gamblers with higher levels of

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depressive symptoms exhibited more severe gambling behavior compared to those low in depressive symptoms, in the form of increased urges to gamble and greater duration of gambling during in-laboratory slot machine play.

The result of hypothesis two indicates that peer pressure has an influence on gambling behaviour. This implies that people who has friends who gamble are likely to be influenced to try out gambling. Put differently the peer you keep can influence you to gamble either directly (by telling you to bet on a game) or indirectly (by you seen them win gamble bet) which will make you want to try out gambling. So it can be said that, young people's gambling is facilitated by their peer group. This finding is in line with the findings of Abdulbaqi et al (2019) stated that there is significant relationship between peer influence and engagement in gambling. A person that is associated with friend that participates in gambling is also vulnerable to gambling related activities. This can be justified based on the fact that an individual who fails to conform to group norms may face social rejection. This study also agrees with that of Fabiansson (2008) who reported that the majority of her participants were introduced to gambling by their peers. Gambling problems among young people appear to be related to peer gambling. Similarly, problem gamblers are more interested in gambling than non-problem gamblers if their first gambling experience was with their peers.

The result of hypothesis three indicates that income level has an influence on gambling behaviour. This implies that the amount of income (low or high) play a major role in gambling. It was noticed that the poor gamble more. This is as a result of them trying to get rich quick idea. Which they think gambling will likely help them get out of poverty. The rich is also not left out of gambling. The findings also points to the fact that the rich also gamble to increase the amount of income they have. The findings of this study is in line with that of McComb and Hanson (2009) who showed that abstention from gambling amounted to an average of 65 percent among respondents in the highest two income categories compared to 78.5 percent among respondents in the poorest two categories. The abstention rate decreased as income increased. The lowest abstention rate was recorded in the middle-income category. The finding also agrees with that of Orford et al (2007) who state that pathological gambling is characterized by an unequal socioeconomic distribution. Individuals from lower-income and ethnic minority groups and communities reported higher rates of pathological gambling than the general population. Individuals with higher economic need, such as people who are poor compared with relevant others or victims of inequality, were more likely to engage in pathological gambling.

The result of hypothesis four indicates that residence (urban or rural) has an influence on gambling behaviour. This implies that people's

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residence play important role in predisposing them to gambling behaviour. The findings show that people that live in areas were gambling shop or that are in proximity gambling stimulating environment will likely gamble. While on the other hand, people that stays in an environment that are not gambling stimulating will likely not gamble. This finding is in line with the findings of Barnes et al (2011) Residence has influences on gambling behavior are important to understand because localities can control the sanction and location of gambling opportunities (e.g., lottery and slot machine venues are more common in disadvantaged neighborhoods as compared with more affluent neighborhoods). Individuals living in disadvantaged neighborhoods were more likely to report higher frequencies of gambling behaviors and gambling problems than those who did not live in disadvantaged neighborhoods. Also the findings of this study agrees with that of Wilson et al (2006) who stated that the proximity or physical access to gambling venues might be what links neighborhood disadvantage to gambling activities and problems. In Montreal, Canada, students attending high schools in lower socio-economic status neighborhoods (with a higher concentration of gambling venues) as compared with more affluent neighborhoods (where gambling venues are less common), are 40 % more likely to gamble.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter deals with the following; summary of the study, recommendations, suggestion for further studies, conclusion, limitation of the studies and finally contribution to knowledge.

5.1 Summary of the Study

This study had its aim on investigate the factors influence of gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State. The study was carried out in Rivers State and 300 undergraduate students were selected through systematic sampling technique for the study. The theoretical frameworks guiding the study are social learning theory. Literature of previous researchers and scholars on gambling behaviour was reviewed with concentrations on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students. Data gathered were analyzed and the results were discussed so as to give relevance to the study data obtained from the field. The result was tested using simple linear regression and independent sample t-test. It was found that there is a significant relationship between depression and gambling behaviour, peer pressure and gambling behaviour, income level and gambling behaviour and place of residence and gambling behaviour.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made for the reduction of gambling behaviour among undergraduate

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students who such gambling interferes with their study.

The parents or guardians should be enlightened on the significance of continued parenting on youths. This will help in the collaborative efforts to identify possible gambling related behaviour and problems among youths and provide appropriate cautioning and help.

Gambling related issues should be legislated upon to curb the indiscriminate establishment of gambling centers' in the country.

Psychologist should intensify their effort to organize seminars/conferences on the implications of gambling processes on youths' behaviour and general wellbeing.

Youths should adopt healthy attitudes toward gambling, such that they recognize it is not a way to make money, nor is it a healthy way to escape from life stressors. Youths should adopt other non-risky activities to derive pleasure and excitement.

There should be a national committee that will be set up to streamline the frivolous and appealing massive advertisement undertaking by gambling organization.

The University, through its entrepreneurial center should empower students on vocational training, with the aim of profit making to reduce involvement in gambling.

The University should also organize an orientation program to educate the students on the effect of peer pressure on gambling behaviour.

5.4 Suggestions for further Study

A new study with a focus on influence of personality traits on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students should be carried out by other researchers.

A new study with a focus on relationship between gambling and antisocial behaviour among undergraduates students in Rivers State should be investigated by subsequent researchers.

A replication of this study should be carried out using other statistical techniques to ascertain the validity and reliability of the present findings.

A new study with a focus on the role of smartphone on gambling behaviour among young adults.

A replication of this study should be carried out with increased sample size and scope of the study area for easy generalization of the findings.

5.2 Conclusions

From the analysis and findings of this study on the factors influence of gambling behaviour among undergraduate students in Rivers State, the following conclusions were made:

Depression as observed in this study is vital factors that influence gambling behaviour among undergraduate students to a greater extent. Students who experience depression may see gambling as a means of overcoming their depression. This means that when people feel depressed, some go to gambling centers to while away time. When this is done repeatedly,

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it leads to tolerance which eventually leads to dependence on gambling.

Peer Pressure as observed in this study is an important factor of gambling behaviour. Students who has peers that gamble, are likely to be influenced directly or indirectly to try out gambling. This means that student's peer group creates problematic gambling if the peer group is involved in gambling behaviour.

Income level as observed in this study is vital factor that influences gambling among undergraduate students to a greater extent. Students who have low or high income level will likely see gambling as a means of trying to increase their income for does with low income while students with high income level may gamble because of the increased income with them.

Residence as observed in this study is an important determinant of gambling behaviour. Students who stay in areas where betting shop, casinos and other forms of gambling is common will likely engage in gambling. From the finding also it can be said that proximity to gambling shop, casinos and other form of gambling increases once chance of gambling.

5.5 Limitations of the study

One unavoidable limitation surrounding the study is that the questionnaire depended seriously on the honest reaction of the respondents which may not be a reflective of their true position of the state of affairs. The researcher assured the respondents of

confidentiality which ensured that honest response was given.

The availability and accessibility of data to enable efficient documentation as it was quite a task laying hand on sources of information for the literature review. The researcher was able to reach out to senior colleagues and librarian in other universities to get material need for the study.

One unavoidable limitation surrounding the study is that the physiological and psychological condition of respondents, which may have a negative influence on their responses, based their health or psychological conditions. The research ensured that systematic sampling method was followed to minimize selection of respondents with either physiological or psychological condition that can affect their response.

5.6 Contribution to knowledge

This study is unique in the sense that it was carried out in a unique environment where such study have not been conducted. The study examined and brings to the fore the influence of depression, peer pressure, income level and place of residence on gambling behaviour in Rivers State. The findings have exposed the public to the impacts of depression, peer pressure, income level and place of residence on gambling behaviour in Rivers State and have added to literature on gambling behaviour among undergraduate students.

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Department of Educational Psychology Guidance and Counseling
Faculty of Education,
University of Port Harcourt.

Dear Respondent,

I am an undergraduate student of the above named department and institution. I am undertaking a study on “**Factors Influencing Gambling Behaviour Among Undergraduate Students In Rivers State**”. Could you please fill out the questionnaire by putting tick (√) in the appropriate column. Be assured, information given will be used basically for the purpose of this study and will be treated confidentially.

Thanks for your anticipated cooperation.

Yours Sincerely

Ugwu, Chiagugom Rebecca

Researcher

FACTORS INFLUENCING GAMBLING BEHAVIOUR QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire is for research work. It is meant to seek your sincere opinion on your experience; your answers will be treated as confidential and used only for the purpose of this study.

Section A: Demographic Inventory

Please fill in the information appropriately

Indicate your preferred opinion with a (√) tick

1. Income Level: high low
2. Resident: Urban Rural

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Part B:

Instructions: Please read each item below to see if the statements reflect your experience. Indicate a (✓) tick in the appropriate box that best expresses your experience. Below is the key to your experience column.

Strongly Agree - SA= 4

Agree - A = 3

Disagree - D = 2

Strongly Disagree - SD =1

Section B. Depression Scale (DPS)

N/S	Items	SA	A	D	SD
1	I feel sleeplessness whenever I loss bet				
2	I loss appetite when I loss a bet for days				
3	Any time I place a bet, I am always nervous based on the outcome				
4	I feel stressed when I play gambling game				
5	I am always sad after playing a gamble				

Section C: Peer Pressure Scale (PPS)

N/S	Items	SA	A	D	SD
1	My friends introduced me to betting				
2	I learnt betting tips from other players that are my friends				
3	I and my friends discuss betting strategies with friends before placing a bet				
4	We bet together with members of my club				
5	I dislike betting but just don't want talk about it because I think my friends will not like it.				

Section D: Gambling Behaviour Scale (GBS)

N/S	Items	SA	A	D	SD
1	Has gambling made you careless of the welfare of yourself or your family?				
2	Have you ever sold anything to finance gambling?				
3	Has gambling caused a decrease in your ambition or efficiency?				
4	Have you ever lost time from work or school due to gambling?				
5	Has gambling affected your reputation?				
6	Have you ever borrowed to finance your gambling?				
7	Have you ever felt remorse after gambling?				
8	Have you ever been reluctant to use 'gambling money' for normal expenditures?				
9	Have you often gambled until losing your last penny?				

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10	Has gambling caused you to have difficulty sleeping?				
11	After losing, have you felt you must return as soon as possible and win back your losses?				
12	After a win, have you felt a strong urge to return and win more?				
13	Have you ever gambled longer than you had planned?				
14	Have you ever committed, or considered committing, an illegal act to finance gambling?				
15	I use a smart phone and other wireless devices to bet				

APPENDIX DATA

S/N	DPS	PPS	GBS
1	16	12	47
2	18	18	51
3	16	17	51
4	13	13	45
5	12	13	48
6	12	14	43
7	12	14	43
8	12	13	43
9	12	12	40
10	12	12	44
11	12	14	43
12	15	13	41
13	14	10	45
14	12	12	45
15	12	12	43
16	14	12	45
17	12	12	42
18	9	12	42
19	12	12	45
20	15	12	40
21	12	12	38

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22	13	11	44
23	12	14	41
24	13	13	41
25	12	12	44
26	15	13	43
27	17	14	50
28	19	15	36
29	16	16	45
30	17	12	45
31	17	14	46
32	17	14	46
33	15	14	35
34	14	15	49
35	17	13	46
36	17	12	48
37	11	12	43
38	17	17	52
39	12	15	53
40	17	14	53
41	13	17	49
42	18	13	50
43	16	17	51
44	17	13	50
45	15	16	53
46	12	12	46
47	12	12	44
48	12	9	41
49	11	14	42
50	12	13	45
51	13	17	46
52	13	12	43
53	14	12	42

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54	15	12	40
55	12	12	47
56	13	12	41
57	14	12	43
58	12	10	40
59	12	14	39
60	12	12	46
61	14	14	38
62	12	14	42
63	14	12	45
64	12	12	45
65	12	14	45
66	18	18	49
67	17	18	46
68	16	15	49
69	12	12	39
70	15	12	43
71	15	12	44
72	14	12	40
73	12	12	38
74	15	12	40
75	14	14	44
76	11	14	44
77	17	17	53
78	16	12	46
79	12	13	45
80	12	12	42
81	12	7	43
82	16	17	51
83	17	16	45
84	17	16	50
85	16	17	53

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88	14	18	53
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90	18	13	45
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92	15	16	43
93	18	18	46
94	18	18	51
95	17	16	50
96	18	16	53
97	17	18	51
98	17	18	49
99	18	18	53
100	18	16	49
101	17	17	53
102	18	17	53
103	17	16	51
104	18	15	50
105	18	16	51
106	18	17	51
107	18	12	52
108	16	15	34
109	13	12	43
110	16	15	40
111	16	11	36
112	16	16	38
113	17	17	35
114	17	15	36
115	17	15	43
116	18	20	53
117	12	16	48

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118	18	17	53
119	17	13	43
120	17	18	48
121	18	18	49
122	18	18	48
123	17	15	51
124	17	13	49
125	17	18	45
126	12	12	45
127	15	12	48
128	15	12	42
129	12	13	40
130	17	13	43
131	12	14	45
132	12	12	43
133	12	13	45
134	11	12	46
135	12	14	42
136	14	12	42
137	15	12	45
138	12	13	45
139	13	14	45
140	16	13	46
141	12	15	49
142	12	12	41
143	12	11	40
144	12	12	46
145	12	13	44
146	14	15	43
147	14	16	46
148	15	13	45
149	13	13	45

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152	11	11	42
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154	16	14	47
155	14	15	51
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169	12	14	45
170	15	12	41
171	15	11	47
172	12	12	43
173	12	12	40
174	15	12	42
175	17	16	49
176	12	16	46
177	12	13	43
178	17	12	49
179	18	18	49
180	17	14	44
181	17	16	46

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183	12	12	39
184	16	13	45
185	13	15	46
186	16	15	48
187	15	16	45
188	12	12	39
189	17	12	44
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191	12	15	48
192	17	15	45
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194	12	12	43
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200	12	12	41
201	17	12	46
202	17	12	43
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204	15	12	45
205	16	13	47
206	14	16	44
207	18	15	47
208	17	13	39
209	18	14	46
210	18	16	48
211	18	14	47
212	14	15	45
213	17	13	52

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214	18	14	42
215	18	12	49
216	14	14	43
217	18	17	53
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220	17	17	52
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242	17	13	48
243	12	14	45
244	13	14	43
245	12	13	42

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271	10	16	45
272	10	18	53
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274	13	17	56
275	17	15	51
276	17	10	52
277	12	16	50

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278	17	16	51
279	16	12	46
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283	15	16	51
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292	13	15	50
293	20	18	44
294	10	14	43
295	14	14	46
296	13	14	33
297	18	14	42
298	14	14	35
299	13	14	32
300	14	13	34

Chiagugom Rebecca Eze (Nee Ugwu) and Chiegeonu Maria Ugwu (Nee Ofielu)

Regression

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Gambling Behaviour	2.5567	1.21864	300
Peer_Pressure	2.4267	1.22868	300

Correlations

		Gambling Behaviour	Peer_Pressure
Pearson Correlation	Gambling Behaviour	1.000	.942
	Peer_Pressure	.942	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Gambling Behaviour	.	.000
	Peer_Pressure	.000	.
N	Gambling Behaviour	300	300
	Peer_Pressure	300	300

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Peer_Pressure ^b		Enter

Chiagugom Rebecca Eze (Nee Ugwu) and Chiegeonu Maria Ugwu (Nee Ofielu)

a. Dependent Variable: Gambling Behaviour

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.942 ^a	.887	.887	.40955

a. Predictors: (Constant), Peer_Pressure

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	394.053	1	394.053	2349.321	.000 ^b
	Residual	49.984	298	.168		
	Total	444.037	299			

a. Dependent Variable: Gambling Behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Peer_Pressure

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.289	.052		5.520	.000
	Peer_Pressure	.934	.019	.942	48.470	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Gambling Behaviour

T-Test

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Low_Income	154	42.1629	11.1918	.04008
High_Income	146	33.5453	10.9999	.04105

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Low_Income	88.945	153	.000	8.56494	3.4858	3.6441
High_Income	87.100	145	.000	9.57534	3.4942	3.6565

Regression

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Depression ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Gambling Behaviour

Chiagugom Rebecca Eze (Nee Ugwu) and Chiegeonu Maria Ugwu (Nee Ofielu)

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.917 ^a	.840	.840	.48799

a. Predictors: (Constant), Depression

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	373.074	1	373.074	1566.685	.000 ^b
	Residual	70.963	298	.238		
	Total	444.037	299			

a. Dependent Variable: Gambling Behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Depression

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.234	.076		-3.085	.002
	Depression	.942	.024	.917	39.581	.000

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T-Test

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Rural	133	40.094	10.283	.03797
Urba	167	39.004	11.824	.07561
n				

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Rural	98.619	132	.000	3.74436	3.6693	3.8195
Urba	38.412	166	.000	2.90419	2.7549	3.0535
n						

Chiagugom Rebecca Eze (Nee Ugwu) and Chiegeonu Maria Ugwu (Nee Ofielu)